

a microscope (1000X). Mortality of larvae in the untreated control was 0.3% at 7 DAT and 0.7% at 14 DAT. Mortality of the treated insects was adjusted using Abbott's formula (see table).

The results indicate that *A.cal* NPV is pathogenic to *M. separata*. Differences in insect mortality were greater at 14 DAT. Treated insects that died without being affected by the virus were those that failed to eat during the first few days.

Effects of the viruses in the field would depend on application method and formulation to give proper distribution-deposition and protection from ultraviolet and other adverse factors. The virus is projected to be

Mortality of *Mythimna separata* (Walk.) treated with nuclear polyhedrosis virus.^a

Treatment		Mortality ^c (%)	
Virus	Dosage ^b (PIB/ml)	7 DAT	14 DAT
<i>A. cal</i> NPV	6.675×10^4	3.2 b	6.7 d
	6.675×10^5	10.0 ab	23.3 c
	6.675×10^6	16.3 ab	31.7 bc
	6.675×10^7	15.7 ab	36.7 b
	6.675×10^8	34.7 a	83.3 a
<i>Ms</i> NPV	3.540×10^4	3.0 c	3.3 d
	3.540×10^5	23.7 b	36.7 b
	3.540×10^6	35.7 b	53.3 ab
	3.540×10^7	41.0 ab	83.3 a
	3.540×10^8	62.0 a	96.7 a

^aThirty 2d-instar larvae replication, 3 replications/treatment. ^bPIB = polyhedral inclusion bodies. ^cMeans in a column followed by common letter are not significantly different by Duncan's multiple range test at 5% level.

used at Solrice farm next year, together with the parasite *Apanteles ruficrus* Haliday (Braconidae -

Hymenoptera), to control *M. separata*. □

Rice leafroller (LF) complex in Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India

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During 1985–86 rabi (winter Nov planting), recommended chemicals did not give adequate control of LF in the Madurai Agricultural College Farm. The larvae were collected periodically and reared to adults.

We found that LF is a complex of three species: *Cnaphalocrocis*

Survey of rice LF in Madurai, India, 1985.

Date collected	LF adults that emerged (no.)		
	<i>C. medinalis</i>	<i>M. patnalis</i>	<i>M. ruralis</i>
26 Sep	107	115	1
27 Sep	25	17	–
28 Sep	43	46	–
29 Sep	30	30	1
30 Sep	13	3	–
1 Oct	29	25	1
2 Oct	45	38	–
10 Oct	4	16	–
14 Oct	2	7	–
Total	298	297	3

medinalis, *Marasmia patnalis*, and *Marasmia ruralis*. The first two were abundant on all sampling dates (see

table). Insecticides need to be screened against all three LF species. □

Effect of 3 granular insecticides on brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal) in the Easternghat Highland Zone, Koraput, India

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In the Easternghat Highland Zone, Koraput district, India, serious BPH outbreaks were observed on irrigated

Effect of granular insecticides on BPH population and rice yield at Semiliguda, Koraput, India, 1981.^a

Insecticide	Adults/hill (treatment at 15 DT)		Nymphs/hill (treatment at 35 DT)		Yield (t/ha)
	10 DAT	20 DAT	10 DAT	20 DAT	
Untreated	13.7 d	59.0 e	27.0 d	0.0	0.0
BPMC	4.7 a	51.7 de	7.3 b	27.7 b	1.5 a
Carbofuran	5.7 ab	35.7 a	6.3 b	34.7 b	1.8 a
Isoprocarb	7.0 bc	42.3 abc	4.3 a	21.0 a	1.7 a
Phorate	8.0 bc	43.3 bc	19.0 cd	0.0	0.0
Disulfoton	8.7 c	41.3 ab	13.0 c	0.0	0.0
Quinalphos	9.3 c	49.3 cd	18.3 cd	0.0	0.0

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 1% level after logarithmic transformation. DT = days after transplanting.